

Hetero-ring Formations with Thiocarbohydrazide. Part III. Reactions of Substituted Thiocarbohydrazides.

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Two different methods of preparation of thiocarbohydrazide are known of which one is due to Curtius and Heidenreich (*J. pr. Chem.*, 1895, ii, 52, 586) and the other is due to Guha and De (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1924, 125, 1215). Though thiocarbohydrazide and a few of its typical reactions and a number of heterocyclic compounds derived from it have been studied (Guha and De, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1924, 1, 141 ; 1926, 2, 225) no alkyl or aryl substituted derivative of this compound is known. Two extremely reactive hydrazino groups are present in thiocarbohydrazide, of which one can be made inert by substitution. So, it was expected that though substituted and unsubstituted thiocarbohydrazides form members of the same family they will react differently towards different ring-closing agents. With this object in view, which has been fully realised, aryl-substituted thiocarbohydrazides have been prepared by a new method and their behaviour towards various types of organic substances has been investigated. 1-Phenyl-, 1-tolyl- and 1:1'-phenyl-methyl-thiocarbohydrazides * have been prepared by the action of hydrazine hydrate upon phenyl-, *m*-tolyl- and methyl-phenyl-dithiocarbazine thus:—

(R=Phenyl or tolyl ; R'=H or methyl).

* The reaction proceeds mainly in the direction as indicated, but along with the phenyl-substituted thiocarbohydrazide there is always obtained a trace of a substance (m.p. 176-177°; N, 28.44; S, 18.44 per cent.) soluble in alkali but insoluble in water and alcohol which could not be studied further for want of a sufficient quantity of this substance.

The action of aldehydes and ketones proceeds in the normal way to yield the corresponding thiocarbohydrazones (VII-XII).

The ring-closure of the aldehyde-thiocarbohydrazones has been effected by the oxidising action of ferric chloride; the resulting thio-biazole derivatives may be represented either by formula (a) or by (b) depending upon the question as to from what part of the molecule a hydrogen atom should tautomerise to convert the thioketonic sulphur into a thiol group.

As the oxidation products could not be hydrolysed by boiling with concentrated hydrochloric acid, and no phenylhydrazine could be traced in the solution thus treated, the formula (b) where the phenylhydrazino group is attached to the thio-biazole ring by a double linking has been rejected. Thus 2-phenyl-5-phenylhydrazino-1:3:4-thiodiazole (XIII), 2-cinnamyl-5-phenylhydrazino-1:3:4-thiodiazole (XIV) and 2-*p*-nitrophenylhydrazino-1:3:4-thiodiazole (XV) have been obtained from (VII), (IX) and (VIII) respectively.

The action of *o*-chlorobenzaldehyde does not only yield a thiocarbohydrazone but it goes a step further and the thiocarbohydrazone first formed gives 2-phenylhydrazino-6:7-benzo-1:3:4-thio-

heptadiazine (XVI) with the loss of a molecule of hydrochloric acid, thus :

That the sulphur atom is present as a member of the ring is proved by the fact that the compound cannot be desulphurised by treatment with mercuric oxide.

Phenylthiocarbohydrazone reacts with phenanthraquinone and acenaphthaquinone to yield phenylhydrazones of 2:3-phenanthro-6-keto-1:4:5-oxdiazine (XVII) and 2:3-acenaphtho-6-keto-1:4:5-oxdiazine (XVIII). The first stage of the reaction consists in the formation of thiocarbohydrazone, thus :

which then assumes the azo-structure by the migration of one hydrogen atom, thus :

The azo-compound then loses a molecule of hydrogen sulphide to give rise to an oxdiazine compound, thus :

m-Tolylthiocarbohydrazone similarly gives a compound (XIX) with phenanthraquinone.

It will be seen that this reaction is quite different from those observed by Guha and De in the case of thiocarbohydrazone and o-diketones like benzil, acenaphthaquinone, camphorquinone, alloxan, phenanthraquinone and isatin when 3-thio-keto-1:2:4:5-hepta-tetrazines and di-phenanthra-(and di-isatino)-thiocarbohydrazone were respectively formed (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 2, 225).

One molecule of phenylthiocarbohydrazone reacts with one molecule of phenanthraquinone-monoxime to form an oxheptatriazine compound (XX), thus:

The behaviour of thiocarbohydrazone itself towards the monoxime has, however, been found to take place in a quite different manner by Guha and De (*loc. cit.*) when a thioketo-bis-triazine compound is formed.

Isatin reacts with phenylthiocarbohydrazone to yield a thiodiazine, thus:

Action of β -Ketonic Esters and 1:4-Diketones.

The hydrazones and oximes of β -ketonic esters easily give up alcohol and are converted into pyrazolones (*cf. J. pr. Chem.*, 39, 153; 52, 23, 45; 51, 43, 140, 157; *Ber.*, 28, 2731; *Annalen*, 922, 5; *Ber.*, 19, 219). De (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1926, 3, 30) has prepared carbamido- and carbothioamido-pyrazolones by treating semi- and thiosemi-carbazones of acetoacetic ester by the action of alcoholic ammonia. In the present instance, phenylthiocarbohydrazone has been found to react with acetoacetic ester to yield first of all a phenylthiocarbohydrazone (XXII) which loses a molecule of alcohol on treatment with sodium ethoxide to yield 1-carbothiophenylhydrazido-3-methyl-5-pyrazolone (XXIII) thus:—

With acetylacetone it reacts readily to yield 2-phenylhydrazino-5:8-dimethyl-1:3:4-thio-octadiazine (XXIV). The possible heptadiazine formula (XXIVa) has been rejected on the ground that the

compound actually isolated is insoluble in alkali and cannot be desulphurised by mercuric oxide.

Blaise (*Compt. rend.*, 1921, 172, 221) has shown that acetyl-acetone reacts with semicarbazide to yield a disemicarbazone in the first stage which gives N-carbamido-2: 5-dimethylazole by the loss of one molecule of semicarbazide. A comparison of the above two reactions would suggest that the thiol-hydrogen atom of phenylthio-carbohydrazide is more easily attacked by a hydroxyl than by an ethoxyl group.

Action of Halogenated Ketones and Esters.

Condensation of thiosemicarbazides with ω -bromacetophenone leads simultaneously to the formation of thiodiazine and thiodiazole derivatives (Bose, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1924, 1, 53; 1925, 2, 95) with preponderance of the first compound. The behaviour of the ω -bromoketone towards 1-phenylthiocarbohydrazide is analogous to Bose's reaction with this difference, however, that the reaction proceeds in this case only in one direction with the exclusion of the thiodiazole compound, thus:—

The alternative formula (XXVa) has been rejected on the ground that a compound containing the group ($:N.NH_2$) would have formed compounds with aldehydes very readily, whereas the compound actually isolated does not do so.

By analogy with the above reaction it was expected that monochloroacetic ester would form a compound of the following formula,

but the compound isolated possesses a hydrazino group as is proved by the fact that it readily forms a benzylidene derivative with benzaldehyde. This difference in behaviour of *o*-bromoacetophenone and monochloroacetic ester can only be accounted for by assuming that the ketonic group of the former reacts with the hydrazino side of the hydrazide to form bromoacetophenone-phenylthiocarbohydrazone which then loses a molecule of hydrobromic acid to form the thiodiazine ring; whereas, with monochloroacetic ester one molecule of HCl is eliminated first forming a carbethoxy-methylthioether which in its turn loses a molecule of alcohol, thus:—

Action of ω -Bromoacetophenone and Chloroacetic ester on Aldehyde-phenylthiocarbohydrazones.

As there is no hydrogen atom available in the farthest nitrogen atom of the aldehyde-phenylthiocarbohydrazone, the (OH) and (OEt) groups of the intermediate products take away the necessary hydrogen atoms from the phenylhydrazino side and are eliminated

in the shape of water and alcohol respectively, to yield thiodiazine derivatives (XXVII), (XXIX) and (XXX) thus:—

Compounds (XXVII) and (XXIX) on hydrolysis give compounds which react very readily with aldehydes and mustard oils proving the presence of reactive hydrazino groups in the hydrolyse products.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Phenylthiocarbonylhydrazide (I).—Hydrazine hydrate (2.5 g.) was added to methylphenyldithiocarbazine (10 g.) in alcoholic suspension and the mixture shaken when the reaction began at once with evolution of heat. The mixture was then heated under reflux for about two hours, filtered after staying overnight and the separated crystalline mass was washed with benzene to dissolve

away the adhering tarry matters and crystallised successively from boiling water and alcohol in white rectangular plates, m.p. 149-150° (yield 2.5 gms.).

It is soluble in alcohol, acetic acid, pyridine and caustic alkalis sparingly soluble in chloroform, acetone, benzene, toluene and hydrochloric acid. (Found: N, 30.62; S, 17.02. $C_7H_{10}N_4S$ requires N, 30.77; S, 17.58 per cent.).

About 0.2 g. of a substance insoluble in water and alcohol was obtained from the reaction mixture.

The Hydrochloride (II).—1-Phenylthiocarbonylhydrazide was dissolved in boiling water and stirred with an excess of hydrochloric acid; on cooling, white crystalline plates separated out, m.p. 181°. It becomes light brown on exposure to the air. (Found: N, 25.91. $C_7H_{10}N_4S$, HCl requires N, 25.68 per cent.).

Ethyl m-Tolyldithiocarbazine (III) was prepared by adding carbonbisulphide (20 g.) and potassium hydroxide (11 g.) dissolved in water under cooling to a solution of *m*-tolylhydrazine (24 g.) dissolved in 75 c.c. of alcohol. Ethyl bromide (11 g.) was then added to it under cooling; the solution after standing for some time separated crystals which were filtered, washed with alcohol and crystallised from the same solvent in white plates, m.p. 99°. It dissolves in alkali and is precipitated by acids (yield 2 gm.). (Found: N, 12.02. $C_{10}H_{14}N_2S_2$, requires N, 12.39 per cent.).

m-Tolylthiocarbonylhydrazide (IV).—A mixture of absolute alcohol (10 c.c.), the above carbazine (10 g.) and hydrazine hydrate (10 g.) was heated under reflux for two hours. On cooling, crystals were deposited which were further purified by crystallisation from alcohol in brownish white plates, m.p. 163-164° with decomp. It is soluble in alkali and is precipitated by dilute acids. (Found: S, 16.02. $C_8H_{11}N_4S$ requires S, 16.32 per cent.).

Ethyl 1:1-Phenyl-methyl-dithiocarbazine (V).—This compound was prepared similarly as compound (III). The separated oil possessing the characteristic odour of a thio-ether was shaken with water, extracted with ether, dried with fused calcium chloride, the ether distilled off and the oil was finally distilled under reduced pressure. (Found: N, 12.71. $C_{10}H_{14}N_2S_2$, requires N, 12.44 per cent.).

1:1-Methyl-phenyl-thiocarbonylhydrazide (VI).—The above ester (15 g.) was heated under reflux with 20 c.c. of absolute alcohol and 5 g. of hydrazine hydrate for 2 hours on the water-bath. The insoluble crystalline mass thus obtained was crystallised from a large quantity

of alcohol in white plates, m.p. 228-229° with decomp. (Found: N, 28·78. $C_8H_{11}N_4S$ requires N, 28·57 per cent.).

Benzaldehyde-1-phenylthiocarbonylhydrazone (VII).—Benzaldehyde (1·1 g.) and 4-phenylthiocarbonylhydrazide (1·8 g.) in alcoholic solution heated under reflux for a few minutes when a white insoluble product separated from the solution and was crystallised from acetic acid in white plates, m.p. 185° (yield quantitative). (Found: N, 20·62. $C_{14}H_{14}N_4S$ requires N, 20·74 per cent.).

p-Nitrobenzaldehyde-1-phenylthiocarbonylhydrazone (VIII).—The compound was crystallised from acetic acid in white rectangular plates, m.p. 192° with a red colouration. (Found: N, 22·1. $C_{14}H_{11}O_2N_4S$ requires N, 22·22 per cent.).

Cinnamaldehyde-1-phenylthiocarbonylhydrazone (IX).—It was crystallised from acetic acid in light yellow plates, m. p. 167-198° (yield is almost quantitative). (Found: S, 10·42. $C_{16}H_{16}N_4S$ requires S, 10·82 per cent.).

Salicylaldehyde-1-phenylthiocarbonylhydrazone (X).—The compound was crystallised from a large quantity of alcohol in white needles, m.p. 206° with decomposition (yield is almost quantitative). (Found: N, 19·29. $C_{14}H_{11}ON_4S$ requires N, 19·59 per cent.).

p-Nitrobenzaldehyde-1-m-tolylthiocarbonylhydrazone (XI).—It was crystallised from acetic acid in light yellow rectangular plates, m.p. 165-166°. (Found: N, 21·48. $C_{16}H_{13}O_2N_4S$ requires N, 21·27 per cent.).

Acetone-1-phenylthiocarbonylhydrazone (XII).—A mixture of acetone and 1-phenylthiocarbonylhydrazide was heated under reflux for 1½ hours. On concentration and cooling a crystalline product began to separate out. After standing for about an hour it was filtered and crystallised from the same solvent in white plates, m.p. 162°. (Found: N, 25·21. $C_{10}H_{14}N_4S$ requires N, 25·22 per cent.).

2-Phenyl-5-phenylhydrazino-1:3:4-thiodiazole (XIII).—An aqueous solution of thoroughly powdered benzaldehyde-1-phenylthiocarbonylhydrazone (2 g.) was heated under reflux with an excess of ferric chloride solution for 15 to 20 minutes. The orange-coloured crystalline product thus obtained was filtered, washed with water, boiled with animal charcoal in alcoholic solution for half an hour and filtered hot; orange coloured needle-shaped crystals were obtained from the solution on cooling, m.p. 172°. It is insoluble in acid and alkali. (Found: N, 20·65. $C_{14}H_{12}N_4S$ requires N, 20·82 per cent.).

2-Cinnamyl-5-phenylhydrazino-1:3:4-thiodiazole (XIV).—This compound was prepared exactly in a similar way as the preceding

compound from cinnamic aldehyde-1-phenylthiocarbohydrazone and was crystallised from alcohol in dark red plates. It shrinks at 168° and melts at 173° (yield is quantitative). It is insoluble in acid and alkali. (Found: S, 10.51. $C_{10}H_{14}N_4S$ requires S, 10.88 per cent.).

2-p-Nitrophenyl-5-phenylhydrazino-1:3:4-thiodiazole (XV).—The method of procedure was the same as in the case of the preceding compound. It was crystallised from acetic acid in golden-yellow plates, m.p. 263-264°. (Found: N, 22.52. $C_{14}H_{11}O_2N_4S$ requires N, 22.37 per cent.).

2-Phenylhydrazino-6:7-benzo-1:3:4-thioheptadiazine (XVI).—1-Phenylthiocarbohydrazide (0.9 g.) and *o*-chlorbenzaldehyde (0.7 g.) in alcoholic solution were heated under reflux for ten minutes when a crystalline product separated out. It was filtered hot, washed with alcohol and crystallised from acetic acid in pale yellow plates, m.p. 195°. The compound was proved to be free from chlorine and could not be desulphurised by mercuric oxide treatment. (Found: N, 20.78. $C_8H_{14}N_4S$ requires N, 20.89 per cent.).

ACTION OF DIKETONES AND THEIR MONOXIMES.

Phenylhydrazone of 2:3-Phenanthra-6-keto-1:4:5-oxdiazine (XVII).—A mixture of phenanthraquinone (4 g.) and 1-phenylthiocarbohydrazide (3.5 g.) in acetic acid solution was heated under reflux. The reaction began at once, the solution became dark in colour and hydrogen sulphide began to evolve. After heating for about an hour, the separated red crystalline product was washed with acetic acid and was crystallised from nitrobenzene in reddish green rectangular plates, m.p. above 300°. (yield 1 gm.). It is insoluble in acids and alkalis and produces a deep blue colouration with concentrated sulphuric acid. (Found: N, 16.32. $C_{21}H_{14}ON_4$ requires N, 16.57 per cent.). The compound was proved to be free from sulphur.

m-Tolylhydrazone of 2:3-Phenanthra-6-keto-1:4:5-oxdiazine (XIX).—An acetic acid solution of phenanthraquinone (3.5 g.) and *m*-tolylthiocarbohydrazide (2 g.) was heated under reflux for 1½ hours. The insoluble precipitate thus obtained crystallised from nitrobenzene in reddish green plates, m.p. above 295° (yield 0.8 gm.). It is insoluble in acid and alkali. (Found: N, 16.30. $C_{22}H_{16}ON_4$ requires N, 15.92 per cent.). The absence of sulphur in this compound was also proved.

Phenylhydrazone of 2:3-Acenaphtha-6-keto-1:4:5-oxdiazine (XVIII).—Acenaphthaquinone (3 g.) and 1-phenylthiocarbonylhydrazide (3 g.) in acetic acid solution were heated under reflux for 4.5 hours. The solution on concentration and cooling yielded a solid product which was crystallised from pyridine in shining black needles, m.p. above 300°. It is insoluble in acid and alkali (yield 1 g.). (Found: N, 18.23. $C_{15}H_{12}ON_2$ requires N, 17.95 per cent.).

Phenylhydrazone of 3:4-Phenanthra-7-keto-1:2:5:6-heptaoxtriazine (XX).—Phenanthraquinone monoxime (2.5 g.) and 1-phenylthiocarbonylhydrazide (1.9 g.) in acetic acid solution were heated under reflux for ten minutes. The reaction proceeded vigorously with effervescence due to the rapid escape of hydrogen sulphide. The separated precipitate was filtered from the deep red solution while hot and crystallised from nitrobenzene in reddish green plates, m.p. above 300° (yield 0.7 g.). It is insoluble in acid and alkali. (Found: N, 19.76. $C_{14}H_{10}ON_3$ requires N, 19.82 per cent.).

Phenylhydrazone of 2:3-Isatino-6-keto-1:4:5-thiodiazine (XXI).—A mixture of isatin (2.8 g.) and 1-phenylthiocarbonylhydrazide (3.6 g.) was heated in acetic acid solution under reflux for two to three hours when a red crystalline precipitate separated out, and was crystallised from a large quantity of acetic acid. It becomes brownish in colour at about 260° and does not melt even at 300° at which temperature it becomes perfectly brown (yield 1.5 gm.) (Found: N, 23.62; S, 10.69. $C_{14}H_{11}N_2S$ requires N, 23.89; S, 10.91 per cent.). It is insoluble in alkali.

ACTION OF 1:3-KETONIC ESTERS AND 1:6-DIKETONES.

Phenylthiocarbonylhydrazone of Acetoacetic ester (XXII).—A mixture of 1-phenylthiocarbonylhydrazide (1.8 g.) and acetoacetic ester (1.3 g.) was heated under reflux in alcoholic solution for one hour. A crystalline product separated out on cooling which was crystallised from alcohol in white plates, m.p. 115-116° (yield 1 gm.). It dissolves in alkali and is precipitated by acids. (Found: N, 19.48. $C_{14}H_{13}O_2N_2S$ requires N, 19.04 per cent.).

1-Carbothiophenylhydrazido-3-methyl-5-pyrazolone (XXIII).—Acetoacetic ester (1.3 g.) was added to 1-phenylthiocarbonylhydrazide (1.8 g.) dissolved in absolute alcohol (25 c.c. containing 0.3 g. of metallic sodium) and the mixture was heated under reflux for 15 minutes. The light-yellow solid thus obtained was dissolved in

sodium hydroxide solution and precipitated by an excess of hydrochloric acid. It was crystallised from benzene in white plates, m.p. 142° with decomp. (yield 0·8 gm.). (Found: N, 22·73. $C_{11}H_{11}ON_2S$ requires N, 22·59 per cent.). The above compound was also obtained by heating phenylthiocarbohydrazone of acetoacetic ester with alcoholic sodium ethoxide solution.

2-Phenylhydrazino-5:8-dimethyl-1:3:4-octathiodiazine (XXIV).—A mixture of acetylacetone (1·8 g.) and 1-phenylthiocarbohydrazone (2 g.) was heated under reflux in acetic acid solution for 15 minutes when an insoluble product separated out and was crystallised from a large quantity of acetic acid in white plates, m.p. 230° with decomp. It is insoluble in acid and alkali. (Found: N, 21·80. $C_{15}H_{14}N_2S$ requires N, 21·52 per cent.).

2-Phenylhydrazino-5-phenyl-1:3:4-thiodiazole (XXV).—A mixture of 1-phenylthiocarbohydrazide (0·9 g.) and *w*-bromacetophenone (0·5 g.) was covered with a sufficient quantity of acetic acid and briskly shaken. Much heat was evolved and soon a clear solution was obtained from which after about two hours a white insoluble product separated out. It was crystallised from a large quantity of alcohol in white plates, m.p. 199° (yield 0·8 gm.). It is insoluble in acid and alkali. (Found: N, 19·70. $C_{15}H_{14}N_2S$ requires N, 19·86 per cent.).

Hydrazone of 2:5-Diketo-4-phenyl-tetrahydro-1:3:4-thiodiazine (XXVI).—An alcoholic solution of monochloroacetic ester (3·6 g.) was added to an alcoholic solution (containing 0·3 g. of sodium) of 1-phenylthiocarbohydrazide (5·4 g.) and the mixture was heated under reflux for three hours. Sodium chloride was removed by filtration while hot and the filtrate yielded a brownish solid on concentration and cooling which was crystallised from dilute alcohol in light brown plates, m.p. 152-153° (yield 1 gm.). It dissolves readily in hydrochloric acid. (Found: N, 25·42. $C_9H_{10}ON_2S$ requires N, 25·23 per cent.).

The *benzal derivative* of (XXVI) was crystallised from alcohol in yellow needles, m.p. 159°. (Found: N, 18·31. $C_{16}H_{14}ON_2S$ requires N, 18·06 per cent.).

ACTION OF HALOGENATED KETONES AND ESTERS ON ALDEHYDE-PHENYLTHIOCARBOHYDRAZONES.

2-Salicylaldehydehydrazone of 2:5-Diketo-4-phenyl-tetrahydro-1:3:4-thiodiazine (XXVII).—Monochloroacetic ester (1·2 g.) was

added to salicylaldehyde-1-phenylthiocarbohydrazone (2·8 g.) suspended in alcohol and the mixture heated under reflux for about 45 minutes. The clear solution obtained after half an hour's heating, yielded, on heating for a few minutes more, an insoluble product which was crystallised from a mixture of alcohol and pyridine in white long plates, m.p. 220° (yield quantitative). It is insoluble in acid and alkali. (Found: N, 17·36. $C_{16}H_{14}O_2N_4S$ requires N, 17·18 per cent.).

Hydrolysis of the above Compound: Formation of the Hydrazone of 2:5-Diketo-4-phenyl-tetrahydro-1:3:4-thiodiazine (XXVIII).—When boiled with moderately strong hydrochloric acid for one hour, the above thiodiazine compound went into solution. It was filtered hot, the solution on concentration and cooling yielded a crystalline precipitate which was crystallised from a small quantity of water, m.p. 247-248° (with decomp.). (Found: Cl, 13·87. $C_6H_6ON_2S$, HCl requires Cl, 13·73 per cent.).

Benzalhydrazone of 2:5-Diketo-4-phenyl-tetrahydro-1:3:4-thiodiazine (XXIX).—This compound was similarly obtained as compound (XXVII) from benzaldehyde-1-phenylthiocarbohydrazone and was crystallised from alcohol in white plates, m.p. 189° with decomposition. It is insoluble in hydrochloric acid and dissolves with difficulty in alkali. (Found: N, 18·38. $C_6H_6ON_2S$ requires N, 18·06 per cent.).

Salicylaldehydehydrazone of 2-Keto-4:5-diphenyl-dihydro-1:3:4-thiodiazine (XXX).—A mixture of salicylaldehyde-1-phenylthiocarbohydrazone (2·8 g.) and *w*-bromacetophenone (2 g.) was heated in an alcoholic solution under reflux for fifteen minutes when a crystalline solid separated out which was crystallised from acetic acid in chocolate coloured needles, m.p. 221° (yield 2 gm.). It is insoluble in acid and alkali. (Found: N, 14·82. $C_{22}H_{18}ON_2S$ requires N, 14·51 per cent.).

Our thanks are due to Sir P. C. Ray and Prof. J. C. Ghosh for the kind interest they have taken in this work.

